

CONTENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY MONITORING IN PEDAGOGICAL COLLEGES

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Annotation. This article presents the innovative features of the quality of education in pedagogical colleges, the application in education of educational qualimetry, pedagogical method and method, self-certification, attestation, pedagogical control and other concepts.

Keywords: qualimetry, pedagogical method, attestation, pedagogical control

The content of innovative activity monitoring is determined by the specific characteristics of innovations, the type of educational institution, the specific characteristics of the teacher's pedagogical work, the specific characteristics of the student contingent, etc.

The content of monitoring of innovative activity in pedagogical colleges usually includes the sequence and content of innovative monitoring stages: preparation, strategic-project, tactical-project, initial-information, systematic-information, final-information.

For more diagnostics (data) of standard methods, for compliance with the goals, specific characteristics and conditions of innovative activity, they are referred to their adaptation, modification and even creation of new ones. Below we consider the criteria for evaluating mental qualities used in working with gifted students.

Table 1.

Matrix for assessing the mental qualities of students

Mental qualities	The most important characteristics of mental qualities
Independence	Fixed the question of the cut and unga answer topish abilities. A criminal case has been opened on this fact, an investigation is underway.
Critical	In this article, we will talk about how you can improve your skills and abilities, as well as how to improve your skills and abilities. Opposition to decision-making and acceptance of conditions that contribute to a decrease in ability, doubts about ability
Next sequence	The ability to follow a logical order when considering a problem, the logical validity of thinking; the ability to strictly adhere to the topic of discussion, not to deviate, not to "jump" from one idea to another.
Flexibility	The ability to change a given decision or decision-making method, if they turn out to be wrong, to find new ways of solving, to approach the topic of consideration "from the other side"; freedom from preconceived assumptions, template methods of problem solving; the ability to take into account changes that require changing the formulation of a specific situation and the issue in it, rejecting the previous decision, accepting a new one; the ability to find a way out of a hopeless situation.
Observability	To penetrate deeply into the essence of the issue, into the essence of the issue, to reveal the causes of events, to see the basis of facts, to understand the meaning of what is happening, to be able to foresee the far-sighted

	consequences. The ability to consider the problem in many ways, to understand the phenomenon in its various connections and relationships
Originality	Unpredictability of non-standard decisions, considerations, Assumptions, Conclusions and conclusions; specificity of approaches and assessments

The determination of the level of development of mental qualities is carried out using an expert assessment or by the method of generalizing independent characteristics in pedagogical counseling. A 3-or 5-dimensional measurement is used. According to the number of students with the same level of development of each quality, they assess the degree of its formation in the entire class and make the necessary decisions.

Adapted to determine the orientation of B. The taxonomy of pedagogical goals in the affective field of Blum is useful for teachers and class leaders. Usually, for this, M. The classical method of Rokeach is used, based on the division of direct values by the subjects themselves into two classes: terminal (values-goals) and instrumental (values-tools). Therefore, its results depend not only on the sincerity of the answers, but also on the level of formation of the individual value system and the student's ability to simply understand it.

The question of choosing methods for diagnosing such innovations is also difficult. In addition to the choice of methods, it is necessary to consider what and by what methods the identified signs of the success of innovations are measured.

For the formation of final conclusions, it is useful not only to analyze and explain, but also to correlate the obtained monitoring data with the results of traditional teachers and answer questions: How did innovations affect the education, upbringing and development of students? Innovations, where and how to do, etc.

The content of Monitoring is based on research methods based on indicators of specific criteria: one of the main areas of monitoring is the development of new

objective methods for monitoring the results of school innovations and the transformation of existing objective methods. For this we used:

- to study the effectiveness of school work on the distribution of pedagogical experience;

- learning to improve the qualifications of school teachers on partial assessments of a personalized card for a specific school year;

- to identify requirements, opinions, proposals, evaluate the innovations carried out within the framework of the implementation of the school development program and to question students and their parents in order to determine the level of satisfaction of all participants in the educational process;

- testing the professional qualifications of college employees in assessing the ability to self-development and self-education.

in determining the criteria indicators, we relied on the criteria of the system for assessing the quality of innovative education in pedagogical colleges.(See Table 2)

Table 2

Criteria for the quality assessment system of innovative education in pedagogical colleges

Criteria	Indicators for students.
Ability to understand value	Formation of positive motivation. Know their role and purpose. The ability to choose, decide on targeted and semantic settings for actions and actions
General cultural competence	Awareness of the student in matters of knowledge. Having effective ways to organize free time. The level of education of students. Mastering the knowledge and experience of the activity
Information competence	The ability to independently extract, analyze and select, store and transmit information.

	Ability to create Multimedia products
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As a result of the use of these methods and criteria in the experiment, we found out the direct dependence of monitoring activities on the theoretical foundations of educational innovation: monitoring has a positive effect on the quality of education, if the basic principles of monitoring activity are consistent; consistency, purposefulness, transparency, completeness and reliability of information, taking into account the interdependence of

The problem of monitoring the quality of education and innovations in pedagogical colleges has a different character than in school. The State customer who is interested in the quality of training specialists, the employer comes to the fore.

G.I. Ibrahimov noted that the system of secondary vocational education is faced with the problem of the quality of training of specialists for a number of reasons .

The content of monitoring innovative activities in pedagogical colleges also includes stages. However, these stages in pedagogical pedagogical colleges are characterized by a higher quality supply than in general education.

In the scientific literature, a system of concepts of general qualimetry is introduced: property, quality, efficiency, purpose, result, measurement assessment, indicator, etc.

These concepts can also be fully applied to educational qualimetry. However, their application refers to the process of teaching in an educational institution of a specific type of education and the characteristics inherent in its participants. Here, in addition to the above, the pedagogical method and method, self-certification, attestation, pedagogical control and other concepts are also used.

Qualimetric support includes the following stages: determination of criteria and indicators for evaluating innovations; selection or development of adequate methods for assessing selected objects of qualimetry; implementation of selected methods; processing of assessment results and their interpretation based on established criteria; development of control actions aimed at improving the quality of Education.

Qualimetric supply can affect the state of the educational system if it becomes a natural part of the development process. This means that it must be built taking into account the value-target parameters of professional education, material, technical and human potential, the concept of accepted education, etc.

In addition, innovative activities in pedagogical colleges should be based on systems for quality control of graduate training, which include:

- joint design of quality support and content of education, educational technologies;
- teaching teachers to work with control and evaluation materials;
- creation of methodological manuals with recommendations for the development of qualimetric supply ;
- constant monitoring of the quality of education, the use of new information technologies for processing and storing large volumes of information; a sufficient amount of computer equipment and related software;
- the presence of a system for ensuring the quality of education (or a system for managing the quality of the educational process) in pedagogical colleges, within the framework of which it is possible to design and implement a qualitative provision of an educational system in all disciplines and blocks of disciplines;
- Organization of a special marketing service in pedagogical colleges with the task of studying the labor market, educational services and monitoring the implementation of state educational standards.

The educational system of colleges is formed and developed in the process of introducing and popularizing innovations.

In the innovation process, the following components are distinguished: innovations, the introduction and application of innovative products or services. Innovations (new ideas, knowledge) are the result of completed scientific fundamental and applied research or developments.

Innovative research in pedagogical college education is mainly carried out in the following areas:

- formation of a new content of Education;
- development and implementation of new pedagogical technologies, methods, systems for the development of students;
- creation of new types of educational institutions.

The most important condition for the effectiveness of the innovative activity of any educational institution is the quality of the leader and pedagogical personnel. Even in the materials of the III International Conference on Adult Education (Tokyo, 1972), opinions were formed, first of all, about the special status of a teacher of vocational education, which is determined by the nature and content of the work of this category of workers.

The features of the teacher's activities are as follows.

First of all, the work of a college teacher is associated with education and upbringing of adolescents, therefore, the teacher is primarily a teacher who needs to know the basics of adolescent physiology and psychology, the basics of general and professional pedagogy, be well versed in diagnostic methods and understand educational issues.

Secondly, the work of a teacher of professional education is directly related to production, with the production of finished products, sometimes very complex, so the teacher of vocational education is an engineer, a technologist.

Thirdly, a professional education teacher is a manager who leads a training group in which the need for planning, regulation, correction, organization, control, decision — making arises.

Fourth, a teacher of professional education should be able to communicate with various categories of citizens: teenagers, colleagues, parents, employees of industrial enterprises, social workers outside his institution, etc.

Thus, the specificity of the activities of a professional educational teacher is due to the combination of the above types of activities.

Thus, in pedagogical colleges, monitoring should be related to the control and evaluation component, which aims to determine the correspondence between the goal setting and the results of the educational process.

Monitoring in colleges should include multi-level pedagogical tools that allow quantitative assessment of innovative activities at three levels: project level, implementation level and the level of education achieved by each college graduate.

The system of scientific management of vocational education in colleges as a set of psychological and pedagogical and information blocks implemented in the complex target program of scientific management of professional training of students includes:

- step-by-step technology of psychological management (stages of professional self-determination, professional orientation, professional selection and professional training in colleges);

- technology of automated monitoring of professionally important personal qualities of listeners, its scientific and methodological and software;

- problematic and automated learning technology in the cycle of special disciplines;

- a set of methodological materials: manuals, recommendations and software products for the scientific management of the educational process.

The creation of a unified system for monitoring innovative activities makes it possible to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the quality of educational activities of the college .

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